

Collateral Management Framework

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a model that allows for collateralization adhering to bankruptcy laws. Our theoretical analysis shows that collateralization can always improve recovery and reduce credit risk. If a contract is over-collateralized, its value is equal to the risk-free value. If a contract is partially collateralized, its CSA value is less than the risk-free value but greater than the non-CSA risky value. The estimation results show that the constant term is insignificantly different from zero; the slope coefficient is close to 1 and the adjusted R^2 is very high. This suggests that the implied premium spreads explain nearly all of the market premium spreads.

Key words: unilateral/bilateral collateralization, partial/full/over collateralization, asset pricing, plumbing of the financial system, swap premium spread, OTC/cleared/listed financial markets.

1. Introduction

The reason collateralization of financial derivatives and repos has become one of the most important and widespread credit risk mitigation techniques is that the Bankruptcy Code contains a series of “safe harbor” provisions to exempt these contracts from the “automatic stay”. The automatic stay prohibits the creditors from undertaking any act that threatens the debtor’s asset, while the safe harbor, a luxury, permits the creditors to terminate derivative and repo contracts with the debtor in bankruptcy and to seize the underlying collateral. This paper focuses on safe harbor contracts (e.g., derivatives and repos), but many of the points made are equally applicable to automatic stay contracts.

Under the new regulations (e.g., Dodd-Frank Wall Street Reform Act), certain ‘eligible’ OTC derivatives must be cleared with central counterparties (CCPs) (see Heller and Vause (2012), Pirrong (2011), etc.). Hull (2011) further recommends mandatory CCP clearing of all OTC derivatives. Meanwhile, Duffie and Zhu (2011) suggest a move toward the joint clearing of interest rate swaps and credit default swaps (CDS) in the same clearinghouse.

There are three types of collateralization: full, partial or over. Full-collateralization is a process where the posting of collateral is equal to the current mark-to-market (MTM) value. Partial/under-collateralization is a process where the posting of collateral is less than the current MTM value. Over-collateralization is a process where the posting of collateral is greater than the current MTM value.

Upon default and early termination, the values due under the ISDA Master Agreement are determined. These amounts are then netted and a single net payment is made. All of the collateral on hand would be available to satisfy this total amount, up to the full value of that collateral. In other words, the collateral to be posted is calculated on the basis of the aggregated value of the portfolio, but not on the basis of any individual transaction.

Due to the complexity of quantifying collateralization, previous studies seem to turn away from direct and detailed modeling of collateralization (see Fujii and Takahashi (2012)). For example, Johannes and Sundaesan (2007), and Fujii and Takahashi (2012) characterize collateralization via a cost-of-collateral instantaneous rate (or stochastic dividend or convenience yield). Piterbarg (2010) regards

collateral as a regular asset in a portfolio and uses the replication approach to price collateralized contracts. All of the previous works focus on full-collateralization only.

This article makes a theoretical and empirical contribution to the study of collateralization by addressing several essential questions concerning the posting of collateral. First, how does collateralization affect expected asset prices? To answer this question, we develop a comprehensive analytical framework for pricing financial contracts under different (partial/full/over and unilateral /bilateral) collateral arrangements in different (OTC/cleared/listed) markets.

Our theoretical analysis shows that collateralization can always improve recovery and reduce credit risk. If a contract is over-collateralized (e.g., a repo or cleared contract), its value is equal to the risk-free value. If a contract is partially collateralized (e.g., an OTC derivatives), its CSA value is less than the risk-free value but greater than the non-CSA risky value.

ISDA mid-market swap rates quoted in the market are based on hypothetical counterparties of AA-rated quality or better. Dealers use this market rate as a reference when quoting an actual swap rate to a client and make adjustments based on many factors, such as credit risk, liquidity risk, funding cost, operational cost and expected profit, etc. Unlike most other studies, this study mainly concentrates the analysis on swap adjustments/premia related to credit risk and collateralization, which are to be made to the mid-market swap rates for real counterparties.

Unlike the generic mid-market swap rates, swap premia are determined in a competitive market according to the basic principles of supply and demand. A client who wants to enter a swap contract first contacts a number of swap dealers and asks for a swap rate. After comparing all quotations, the client chooses the most competitive rate. A swap premium is supposed to cover operational, liquidity, funding, and credit costs as well as a profit margin. If the premium is too low, the dealer may lose money. If the premium is too high, the dealer may lose the competitive advantage.

To circumvent this difficulty, this article uses an indirect process to verify the model empirically. We define a *swap premium spread* as the difference between the swap premia of two collateralized swap contracts that have exactly the same terms and conditions but are traded with different counterparties under

different collateral agreements. We reasonably believe that if two contracts are identical except counterparties, the premium spread should reflect the difference between two counterparties' unsecured credit risks only, as all other risks and costs are identical.

Third, what are the effects of counterparty risk and collateralization, alone or combined, on swap premium spreads? We first study the marginal impact of counterparty risk on spreads. CDS premia (the prices of insuring against a firm's default) theoretically reflect the credit risk of the firm. Presumably, differences in CDS premia should be largely attributable to differences in counterparty risk. We estimate a regression model where market swap premium spreads are used as the dependent variable and differences between CDS premia as the explanatory variable. The estimation results show that the adjusted R^2 is 0.7472, implying that approximately 75% of market premium spreads can be explained by CDS spreads. In other words, counterparty risk alone can provide a good but not overwhelming prediction on spreads.

Finally, how does collateralization impact pricing in different markets? Our proprietary data reveal that cleared swaps have dramatically increased since 2011, reflecting the financial institutions' compliance to regulatory requirements. We find evidence that the economical determination of swap rates in cleared markets is the same as that in OTC markets, as all clearinghouses claim that cleared derivatives would replicate OTC derivatives, and promise that transactions through the clearinghouses would be economically equivalent to similar transactions handled in OTC markets.

In fact, our study shows that there are many differences between cleared markets and OTC markets. After much discussion, we come to the conclusion that cleared derivatives are not economically equivalent to their OTC counterparts. These discussions may be of interest to regulators, academics and practitioners.

2. Bilateral Collateralization

Two counterparties are denoted as A and B . The binomial default rule considers only two possible states: default or survival. Therefore, the default indicator Y_j for party j ($j=A, B$) follows a Bernoulli distribution, which takes value 1 with default probability q_j and value 0 with survival probability p_j , i.e.,

$P\{Y_j = 0\} = p_j$ and $P\{Y_j = 1\} = q_j$. The marginal default distributions can be determined by the reduced-form models. The joint distributions of a bivariate Bernoulli variable can be easily obtained via the marginal distributions by introducing extra correlations.

Consider a pair of random variables (Y_A, Y_B) that has a bivariate Bernoulli distribution. The joint probability representations are given by

$$p_{00} := P(Y_A = 0, Y_B = 0) = p_A p_B + \sigma_{AB} \quad (18a)$$

$$p_{01} := P(Y_A = 0, Y_B = 1) = p_A q_B - \sigma_{AB} \quad (18b)$$

$$p_{10} := P(Y_A = 1, Y_B = 0) = q_A p_B - \sigma_{AB} \quad (18c)$$

$$p_{11} := P(Y_A = 1, Y_B = 1) = q_A q_B + \sigma_{AB} \quad (18d)$$

where $E(Y_j) = q_j$, $\sigma_j^2 = p_j q_j$, $\sigma_{AB} := E[(Y_A - q_A)(Y_B - q_B)] = \rho_{AB} \sigma_A \sigma_B = \rho_{AB} \sqrt{q_A p_A q_B p_B}$ where ρ_{AB} denotes the default correlation coefficient and σ_{AB} denotes the default covariance.

For a two-way CSA, each party has an effective collateral threshold and is required to post collateral to the other as exposures arise. The collateral amount at t is given by

$$C(t) = \begin{cases} V^C(t) - H_B & \text{if } V^C(t) > H_B \\ 0 & \text{if } H_A \leq V^C(t) \leq H_B \\ V^C(t) - H_A & \text{if } V^C(t) < H_A \end{cases} \quad (19a)$$

or

$$C(t) = 1_{V(t) > H_B} (V^C(t) - H_B) + 1_{V(t) < H_A} (V^C(t) - H_A) \quad (19b)$$

where $H_B \geq 0$ and $H_A \leq 0$ are the collateral thresholds for parties B and A , and $V^C(t)$ is the CSA value of the contract at time t .

At time T , there are a total of four ($2^2 = 4$) possible states shown in Table 1. The CSA value of the contract is the discounted expectation of the payoffs and is given by the following proposition.

Proposition 3: *The bilateral CSA value of the partially collateralized single-payment contract is given by*

$$V^C(t) = E[L(t, T) X_T | \mathcal{F}_t] - M(t, T) \quad (20a)$$

where

$$L(t, T) = D(t, T) \left[1_{0 \leq V_B^N(t) \leq H_B(t)} I_B(t, T) + 1_{V_B^N(t) > H_B(t)} I_B(t, T) / \bar{I}_B(t, T) \right. \\ \left. + 1_{0 \geq V_A^N(t) \geq H_A(t)} I_A(t, T) + 1_{V_A^N(t) < H_A(t)} I_A(t, T) / \bar{I}_A(t, T) \right] \quad (20b)$$

$$M(t, T) = 1_{V_B^N(t) > H_B(t)} H_B(t) \bar{q}_B(t, T) (1 - \varphi_B(T)) / \bar{I}_B(t, T) \\ + 1_{V_A^N(t) < H_A(t)} H_A(t) \bar{q}_A(t, T) (1 - \varphi_A(T)) / \bar{I}_A(t, T) \quad (20c)$$

where $\bar{I}_j(t, T) = E(I_j(t, T) | \mathcal{F}_t) = E(p_j(t, T) + \varphi_j(T) q_j(t, T) | \mathcal{F}_t)$, $V_j^N(t) = E[I_j(t, T) X_T | \mathcal{F}_t]$, and $j = A$ or B .

Proof: See the Appendix.

Table 1. Payoffs of a bilaterally collateralized contract

This table displays all possible payoffs at time T . In the case of $X_T > 0$, there are a total of four possible states at time T : i) Both A and B survive with probability p_{00} . The contract value is equal to the payoff X_T . ii) A defaults but B survives with probability p_{10} . The contract value is also the payoff X_T . Here we follow the two-way payment rule¹. iii) A survives but B defaults with probability p_{01} . The contract value is the collateralized default payment: $C(T) + \varphi_B(T)(X_T - C(T))$. iv) Both A and B default with probability p_{11} . The contract value is also $C(T) + \varphi_B(T)(X_T - C(T))$. A similar logic applies to the case of $X_T < 0$.

State	$Y_A = 0, Y_B = 0$	$Y_A = 1, Y_B = 0$	$Y_A = 0, Y_B = 1$	$Y_A = 1, Y_B = 1$
Comments	A & B survive	A defaults, B survives	A survives, B defaults	A & B default

¹ There are two default settlement rules in the market. The *one-way payment rule* was specified by the early ISDA master agreement. The non-defaulting party is not obligated to compensate the defaulting party if the remaining market value of the instrument is positive for the defaulting party. The *two-way payment rule* is based on current ISDA documentation. The non-defaulting party will pay the full market value of the instrument to the defaulting party if the contract has positive value to the defaulting party.

Probability		P_{00}	P_{10}	P_{01}	P_{11}
Payoff	$X_T > 0$	X_T	X_T	$C(T) + \varphi_B(T)(X_T - C(T))$	$C(T) + \varphi_B(T)(X_T - C(T))$
	$X_T < 0$	X_T	$C(T) + \varphi_A(T)(X_T - C(T))$	X_T	$C(T) + \varphi_A(T)(X_T - C(T))$

In particular, if $H_A = H_B = 0$ (corresponding to bilateral full-collateralization), and $I_i(t, T)$ and X_T are uncorrelated, we have $L(t, T) = 1$, $M(t, T) = 0$, and thereby $V^C(t) = V^F(t)$. That is to say, under full-collateralization the bilateral CSA value of the contract is equal to the risk-free value.

Using a similar derivation as in Proposition 2, we can easily extend Proposition 3 from one-period to multiple-periods. Suppose that a defaultable portfolio/contract has m netted cash flows. Let the m cash flows be represented as X_i with payment dates T_i , where $i = 1, \dots, m$. Each cash flow may be positive or negative. The bilateral CSA value of the multiple payment contract is given by

$$V^C(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E \left[\prod_{k=0}^{i-1} (L(T_k, T_{k+1})) X_i \mid \mathcal{F}_t \right] - \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} E \left[\prod_{k=0}^{i-1} (L(T_k, T_{k+1})) M(T_i, T_{i+1}) \mid \mathcal{F}_t \right] \quad (21a)$$

where

$$L(T_k, T_{k+1}) = D(T_k, T_{k+1}) \left[1_{0 \leq O_B(T_k, T_{k+1}) \leq H_B(T_k)} I_B(T_k, T_{k+1}) + 1_{O_B(T_k, T_{k+1}) > H_B(T_k)} I_B(T_k, T_{k+1}) / \bar{I}_B(T_k, T_{k+1}) \right. \\ \left. + 1_{0 \leq O_A(T_k, T_{k+1}) \leq H_A(T_k)} I_A(T_k, T_{k+1}) + 1_{O_A(T_k, T_{k+1}) < H_A(T_k)} I_A(T_k, T_{k+1}) / \bar{I}_A(T_k, T_{k+1}) \right] \quad (21b)$$

$$M(T_k, T_{k+1}) = 1_{O_B(T_k, T_{k+1}) > H_B(T_k)} H_B(T_k) \bar{q}_B(T_k, T_{k+1}) (1 - \varphi_B(T_{k+1})) / \bar{I}_B(T_k, T_{k+1}) \\ + 1_{O_A(T_k, T_{k+1}) < H_A(T_k)} H_A(T_k) \bar{q}_A(T_k, T_{k+1}) (1 - \varphi_A(T_{k+1})) / \bar{I}_A(T_k, T_{k+1}) \quad (21c)$$

where $O_j(T_k, T_{k+1}) = E \left[D(T_k, T_{k+1}) I_B(T_k, T_{k+1}) (V^C(T_{k+1}) + X_{k+1}) \mid \mathcal{F}_{T_k} \right]$ and $j = A$ or B .

Similar to Proposition 2, the individual payoffs in equation (21) are coupled and cannot be evaluated separately. The process requires a backward induction valuation.

3. Empirical Results

Swap rate is the fixed rate that sets the market value of a given swap at initiation to zero. ISDA established ISDAFIX in 1998 in cooperation with Reuters (now Thomson Reuters) and Intercapital Brokers

(now ICAP PLC). Each day ISDAFIX establishes average mid-market swap rates at key terms to maturity. These generic benchmark swap rates are based on a rigorously organized daily poll: An ICAP or Reuters representative canvasses a panel of dealers for their par swap rate quotes as of a specified local mid-day time. For any given swap term to maturity, the rate provided by the contributing dealer is the midpoint of where that dealer would itself offer and bid a swap for a certain notional. The mid-market benchmark rate for any given swap tenor is determined as a trimmed mean. Reuters and Bloomberg post the mid-market rates as soon as polling is completed.

Unlike the generic benchmark swap rates, swap premia are determined according to the basic principles of supply and demand. The swap market is highly competitive. In a competitive market, prices are determined by the impersonal forces of demand and supply, but not by manipulations of powerful buyers or sellers. If a premium is set too low, the dealer may lose money. If the premium is set too high, the dealer may lose the competitive advantage.

A swap premium is supposed to cover the expected profit and all the expenses, including the cost of bearing unsecured credit risk. Unfortunately, however, we do not know what percentage of the market swap premium is allocated to the unsecured credit risk, which makes a direct verification impossible.

We obtain a unique proprietary data set from an investment bank (FinPricing (2018)). The data set contains swap contract data, counterparty data (including collateral agreements, recovery rates, etc), and market data. The trading dates are from May 6, 2005 to May 11, 2012. The data show that before 2011 the dealer traded interest rate swaps with a large number of counterparties. But since 2011, the transactions have been concentrated in a few clearinghouses, which reflect financial institutions' compliance with the regulatory requirements. Consequently, we divide the data into two categories: the *OTC data set* containing all the transactions traded with regular counterparties and the *cleared data set* holding all the contracts cleared in CCPs.

We arbitrarily select one pair shown in Table 2.

Table 2: A pair of 20-year swap contracts

This table displays the terms and conditions of two swap contracts. They have different counterparties but are otherwise the same. We hide the counterparty names according to the security policy of the investment bank while everything else is authentic.

	Swap 1		Swap 2	
	Fixed leg	Floating leg	Fixed leg	Floating leg
Counterparty	X		Y	
Effective date	15/09/2005	15/09/2005	15/09/2005	15/09/2005
Maturity date	15/09/2025	15/09/2025	15/09/2025	15/09/2025
Day count	30/360	ACT/360	30/360	ACT/360
Payment frequency	Semi-annually	Quarterly	Semi-annually	Quarterly
Swap rate	4.9042%	-	4.9053%	-
Roll over	Mod_follow	Mod_follow	Mod_follow	Mod_follow
Principal	25,000,000.00	25,000,000.00	25,000,000.00	25,000,000.00
Currency	USD	USD	USD	USD
Pay/receive	Bank receives	Party X receives	Bank receives	Party Y receives
Floating index	-	3 month LIBOR	-	3 month LIBOR
Floating spread	-	0	-	0
Floating reset	-	Quarterly	-	Quarterly

The LIBOR-future-swap curve is presented in Table 3. After bootstrapping the curve, we get the continuously compounded zero rates.

Table 3: USD LIBOR-future-swap curve

This table displays the closing mid prices as of September 15, 2005

Instrument Name	Price
September 21 2005 LIBOR	3.6067%
September 2005 Eurodollar 3 month	96.1050

December 2005 Eurodollar 3 month	95.9100
March 2006 Eurodollar 3 month	95.8100
June 2006 Eurodollar 3 month	95.7500
September 2006 Eurodollar 3 month	95.7150
December 2006 Eurodollar 3 month	95.6800
2 year swap rate	4.2778%
3 year swap rate	4.3327%
4 year swap rate	4.3770%
5 year swap rate	4.4213%
6 year swap rate	4.4679%
7 year swap rate	4.5120%
8 year swap rate	4.5561%
9 year swap rate	4.5952%
10 year swap rate	4.6368%
12 year swap rate	4.7089%
15 year swap rate	4.7957%
20 year swap rate	4.8771%
25 year swap rate	4.9135%

According to equation (21), we also need counterparty-related information, such as recovery rates, hazard rates and collateral thresholds. The CDS spreads and recovery rates are given in Table 4. We can compute the hazard rates via a standard calibration process (see J.P. Morgan [2001]).

Table 4: CDS premia and recovery rates

This table displays the closing CDS premia as of September 15, 2005 and recovery rates

Counterparty name	Bank	Company X	Company Y
6 month CDS spread	0.00031	0.000489	0.000808

1 year CDS spread	0.000333	0.00056	0.001017
2 year CDS spread	0.000516	0.000866	0.00154
3 year CDS spread	0.000664	0.001147	0.002114
4 year CDS spread	0.000848	0.00147	0.002768
5 year CDS spread	0.001012	0.001783	0.003439
7 year CDS spread	0.001334	0.002289	0.004283
10 year CDS spread	0.001727	0.002952	0.005281
15 year CDS spread	0.001907	0.003283	0.005814
20 year CDS spread	0.002023	0.003266	0.006064
30 year CDS spread	0.002021	0.00336	0.006461
Recovery rate	0.39213	0.35847	0.33872

Table 5: CSA agreement

This table provides the collateral thresholds and MTAs under the CSA agreements.

CSA agreement	1		2	
	Bank	Company X	Bank	Company Y
Counterparty name	Bank	Company X	Bank	Company Y
Threshold	0	0	0	0
MTA	500000	500000	500000	500000

Given the above information, we are able to compute the collateralized swap rates. We first use the LMM to evolve the interest rates and then determine the associated CSA-adjusted discount factors as well as the cost of bearing unsecured credit risk according to equation (21). Finally, we calculate the collateralized swap rates via backward induction method. The results are given in table 6.

Table 6: Swap rate results

This table presents the model-implied swap rates and premia as well as the dealer-quoted swap rates and premia, where Swap premium (in bps) = Swap rate – Generic swap rate, and Premium spread = Premium of swap 2 – Premium of swap 1.

	Swap 1		Swap 2		Premium spread	Generic swap rate
	Swap rate	Premium	Swap rate	Premium		
Model-implied	0.048780	0.09 bps	0.048790	0.19 bps	0.10 bps	0.048771
Dealer quoted	0.049042	2.71 bps	0.049053	2.82 bps	0.11 bps	

By taking credit risk and collateralization into account only, we calculate the model-implied swap rates as 0.048780 and 0.048790 shown in Table 6. Consequently, the implied swap premia are 0.09 bps and 0.19 bps. The results imply that only a small portion of a swap premium is attributed to unsecured credit risk. This is in line with the findings of Duffie and Huang (1996), Duffie and Singleton (1997), and Minton (1997). Table 6 shows that the model-implied swap premium spread is quite close to the dealer-quoted swap premium spread, suggesting that the model is fairly accurate in pricing collateralized financial instruments.

The empirical tests corroborate the theoretical prediction on the impact of collateralization on swap rates.

Table 7: Summary statistics of implied swap premium spreads, market swap premium spreads and model-market swap premium spread differentials

All values are displayed in bps. Model-market premium spread differential = Model-implied premium spread – Market-quoted premium spread.

	Max	Min	Mean	Median	Std
Market quoted swap premium spreads	3.08	-5.25	-0.46	-0.15	1.80
Model-implied swap premium spreads	2.10	-5.33	-0.44	0.03	1.73
Model-market premium spread differentials	0.99	-1.18	-0.03	0.11	0.46

We present the estimate of the following regression model.

$$Y = a + bX + \varepsilon \quad (22)$$

where Y is the market swap premium spread, X is the difference between the CDS spreads, a is the intercept, b is the slope, and ε is the regression residual.

We provide empirical evidence that counterparty risk alone plays a significant but not overwhelming role in determining credit-related spreads when contracts are under collateral agreements. Moreover, the slope is 0.0127, implying that a CDS spread of about 100 basis points translates into a swap spread of about 1.27 basis points.

Table 8: Marginal credit risk regression results for the OTC data

This table presents the regression results for the following regression model in the OTC market:

$$\text{MktSwapPremiumSpreads} = a + b \times \text{DifferencesBetweenCDSs} + \varepsilon$$

Market swap premium spreads are used as the dependent variable and differences between CDS spreads as the explanatory variable.

Slope	Intercept	Adjusted R^2	Significance F
0.0127	-2.7E-04	0.7472	1.1E-05

It can be seen from Table 9 that the implied premium spreads explicate nearly all of the market premium spreads with a slope coefficient close to 1. More important, the adjusted R^2 value is 0.9565, implying that approximately 96% of the market premium spreads can be explained by the implied spreads. The empirical results shed light on the economic significance of collateralization. We find evidence that credit risk is not overly important in spreads. Only the combination of credit risk and collateralization can provide a sufficient explanation for these price differences.

Table 9: Credit risk and collateralization combined regression results for the OTC data

This table presents the regression results for the following regression model in the OTC market:

$$\text{MktSwapPremiumSpreads} = a + b \times \text{ImpliedSwapPremiumSpreads} + \varepsilon$$

The market swap premium spreads are used as a dependent variable and the implied swap premium spreads as the explanatory variable.

Slope	Intercept	Adjusted R^2	Significance F
0.9857	4.48E-05	0.9565	3.21E-08

We empirically demonstrate that under the new regulatory rules, derivative are continuously negotiated over-the-counter as usual, and then cleared and settled through a clearinghouse. Since clearinghouses claim that cleared derivatives would replicate OTC derivatives and promise that transactions through the clearinghouses would be economically equivalent to similar transactions handled in OTC markets, swap rates in cleared markets are determined in the same way as those in OTC markets.

Table 10: Statistics of market observed swap premium spreads

This table presents descriptive statistics for market swap premium spreads in both OTC and cleared markets.

All values are expressed in bps.

Market quoted swap premium spreads	Max	Min	Mean	Median	Std
In the OTC data set	3.08	-5.25	-0.46	-0.15	1.80
In the cleared data set	3.51	-4.41	-0.34	-0.21	1.27

There are many reasons to question this practice. First, the results generated by this practice can not be interpreted by any known models or theories. As clearinghouses hide counterparties, we can only see the clearinghouses in the data. The two contracts in each cleared swap pair have exactly the same counterparty (i.e., the same CCP) and terms and conditions but different swap rates. In other words, they

appear to be identical in everything except swap rates. This violates the single value rule: two assets with identical information must be traded at the same price.

Second, there are many differences between cleared markets and OTC markets. The first difference is that cleared derivatives are over-collateralized as all CCPs require initial margins, whereas CSA derivatives in OTC markets are partially collateralized as all CSA counterparties maintain a positive MTA. The second difference is that cleared derivatives are subject to unilateral collateralization because only CCPs have the right to call for collateral, while OTC derivatives are most probably under bilateral collateralization. The third difference is that OTC collateral agreements always set a MTA to avoid the workload associated with a frequent transfer of insignificant amount of collateral between firms, whilst CCPs mark contracts to market daily and charge variation margins in response to changes in market values without a MTA.

The fifth difference is that a CCP mitigates credit risk via novation and multilateral netting. The novation process splits a contract into two – one setting out a sale and the other setting out the countervailing purchase – and substitutes the clearinghouse for the counterparty in each half of the transaction. Accordingly, the clearinghouse takes on credit risk on behalf of the original counterparties. The multilateral netting process enables offsets across market participants, which further ameliorates credit risk (see Cont and Kokholm (2011) and McPartland, et al. (2011)). In general, novation and multilateral netting processes change the risk structure that affects asset prices.

Even trivial variations between cleared and OTC markets can result in potentially large valuation discrepancy (see Pengelly (2011)). Given many differences between them, our theoretical study shows that over-collateralized derivatives in cleared markets are not economically equivalent to their partially collateralized counterparts in OTC markets.

From a dealer's perspective, market making involves costs and executing a transaction in a clearinghouse also entails expenses. Dealers that make markets must be compensated for incurring these costs and expenses. As a consequence, dealers in cleared markets also collect a swap premium for a transaction. However, swap premia charged in cleared markets should be different from those collected in

OTC markets, as cost and risk structures have changed. At least, if two contracts have exactly the same terms and conditions as well as the same counterparty (i.e., the clearinghouse), they should have the same premia, as the swap premia should not be influenced by difference in counterparty credit risk in cleared markets. The discussions above may have important implications for regulators, academics and practitioners. A better understanding of collateralization would enable them to more accurately assess the impact of new regulation on financial markets.

4. Conclusion

We present a comprehensive theoretical framework for pricing collateralized financial contracts based on the fundamental principal and legal structure of CSA agreements. The model can back out differences in asset prices due to collateralized counterparty risk. This is very useful for pricing outstanding defaultable financial contracts.

We find strong evidence that counterparty risk alone plays a significant but not overwhelming role in determining credit-related spreads for collateralized contracts. Only the joint effect of collateralization and credit risk can provide a sufficient explanation for unsecured credit costs. This finding suggests that failure to properly account for collateralization may result in significant mispricing of financial contracts.

We also find evidence that financial institutions are sprinting to comply with the Dodd-Frank Act. In the new practice, contracts are continuously negotiated over-the-counter as usual, but cleared and settled via clearinghouses, as clearinghouses claim that cleared contracts would be economically equivalent to their OTC counterparts. As a result, swap premia in cleared market are determined in a similar way to those in OTC markets. We argue that this practice may not be appropriate because we notice that the clearing mechanics of a clearinghouse change the risk structure and thereby the asset prices. In fact, we find that cleared derivatives are not economically equivalent to their OTC counterparts.

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